

EXPLORING THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NURSES IN HEMODIALYSIS CARE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18385608>

ABSTRACT

Hemodialysis nursing is a specialized and emotionally demanding field that requires not only technical expertise but also compassionate, holistic care for patients with end-stage renal disease. The study aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of nurses working in hemodialysis units in Roxas, Isabela, Philippines. The study utilized descriptive qualitative research design, an in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted in 15 registered nurses currently employed in selected hemodialysis centers. Thematic analysis was used to identify recurring themes from the narratives. The findings revealed seven (7) emerging themes in terms of the lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses such as complex demands of hemodialysis nursing, technical expertise, resiliency, routines, patient-centered care, sense of purpose, and deep nurse-patient relationship. As regards the positive experiences of hemodialysis nurses, four (4) themes emerged such as moments of personal and professional fulfillment, emotional bonding, resilience in action, and daily gratitude as emotional reward. Themes such as struggles with skills gap and clinical competence, managing difficult and rude patients, and emotional impact of patient death and loss were the negative experiences of hemodialysis nurses. Moreover, challenges such as unpredictable and life-threatening effects of dialysis, shortage of staff, suppressed personal stress, technical and operational challenges were found. In addition, deepened understanding of holistic and compassionate care, admiration for patients, and heightened appreciation for personal health and preventive care were ways that changed the nurses' perception of patient care. Lastly, they perceived that peer connection and workplace camaraderie, emotional reliance, and personal coping rituals and self-care practices were the coping mechanisms that help them deal with the stresses and demands of hemodialysis. The study highlighted the critical need for holistic support

systems, continuous training, and policy development that acknowledge the unique challenges faced by hemodialysis nurses.

Keywords: *Hemodialysis nurse, Lived experiences, Challenges, Coping mechanisms*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the role of nurses in hemodialysis care has evolved significantly in response to the growing prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) and end-stage renal disease (ESRD). The increasing number of patients requiring hemodialysis underscores the critical role of specialized nursing care in managing these complex cases. Nursing in the treatment of hemodialysis has great relevance regarding the uninterrupted observation of patients in the period in which the hemodialysis session occurs, and nursing can help save lives and may also avoid possible complications which is the early and accurate diagnosis of intercurrents.

Although hemodialysis nurses play a key role in HD treatment, they should be equipped with the appropriate competencies to provide adequate care to an increasing number of patients. Despite their critical contributions, the lived experiences of nurses in hemodialysis care remain underexplored particularly in low- and middle-income countries like the Philippines, where the burden of chronic kidney disease continues to rise.

In Roxas, Isabela, the number of individuals undergoing hemodialysis continues to rise annually. With this increase, hemodialysis nurses play the role of providing care to the patient in an integral way, contemplating it, creating a mutual relationship of trust and safety between patient and nurse, and giving priority to the care necessary for their treatment.

Research Question

What are the lived experiences of nurses in caring hemodialysis patients?

Research Objectives

1. Explore the lived experiences of nurses in caring hemodialysis patients
2. Identify the memorable or positives experiences of nurses in caring hemodialysis patients.
3. Identify the negative experiences of the nurses in caring hemodialysis patients.
4. Identify the challenges experienced by the nurses in caring hemodialysis patients.
5. Describe how working as a hemodialysis nurse changes perceptions of patient care, chronic illness, and resilience.
6. Understand the coping mechanisms or support systems help the nurses in dealing with the stresses and demands of hemodialysis care.

7. Highlight the most rewarding aspects of working with hemodialysis patients.
8. Generate insight that can inform support system or resources for improving nurse well – being and patient care in hemodialysis unit.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted across various dialysis centers or departments around Roxas, Isabela. Hemodialysis Center A has 8 HD machines with 6 nurses, Hemodialysis Center B has 7 HD machines with 6 nurses, and Hemodialysis Center C has 10 HD machines with 10 nurses. The researcher employed purposive sampling, a non-probability technique that allows for the intentional selection of participants based on specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. The population of the study included 15 registered nurses currently working in a hemodialysis center or department. The researcher formulated interview guide questions to answer the main problem of the study and to facilitate data collection. The researcher used thematic analysis, a method used to identify and interpret patterns or themes in a data set; it often leads to new insights and understanding (Naeem et al., 2023).

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study on the lived experiences of nurses in hemodialysis care. Data from in-depth interviews were thematically analyzed to uncover patterns and insights related to their professional and personal experiences. The emerging themes reflect the complex realities and challenges faced by hemodialysis nurses. The presentation of results is organized by major themes. Each theme presents each participant verbatims that capture the essence of the participants' experiences.

Part 1. Lived Experiences of Hemodialysis Nurse

Hemodialysis nursing is recognized as one of the most demanding areas of clinical practice, requiring a balance of technical expertise, critical thinking, and emotional resilience. These experiences reflect both the complexity of the work and the toll it takes on the nurse's physical and emotional well-being. The generated themes offer valuable insights into the realities of daily practice, the emotional and physical demands of hemodialysis care, and the personal meaning nurses attach to their roles. The following themes encapsulate the essence of their lived experiences and highlight the nature of hemodialysis nursing.

Theme 1: Complex Demands of Hemodialysis Nursing

The themes reflect the multiple aspects of hemodialysis care, emphasizing the physical and mental obstacles that nurses experience daily. Participants underlined:

"My work right now is physically demanding and emotionally intense."
(P1)

“Each day tests my skills and resilience” (P3)
“Every day is a long day. I experience burnout because we spend a long hour on our feet dealing and managing the emotional toll of patients.” (P10)
“Being a hemodialysis nurse is really both challenging and fulfilling” (P15)

Theme 2: Technical Expertise in Hemodialysis Nursing

The theme highlights how important it is for hemodialysis nurse to have technical skills in their daily work. Participants expressed:

“My day starts early, prepping machines” (P1)
“I’ve learned to manage complex machines” (P3)
“I have experience involving technical skills” (P4)
“at dapat knowledgeable sa pag-troubleshoot ng machines” (It is also important to be knowledgeable in troubleshooting dialysis machines.) (P5)

Theme 3: Resiliency Amidst Meaningful Cares

This theme highlights the resilience of hemodialysis nurse, as they face the emotional, mental, and professional challenges of their jobs. Participants noted:

“It’s not an easy job, but it’s meaningful.” (P1)
“having resilience to deal with humans who are undergoing life-sustaining treatment” (P2)
“my experience has been both challenging and fulfilling.it also strengthens my dedication to this vital and meaningful work” (P3)
“It made me feel more fulfilled and connected to my role as a nurse.” (P9)
“it’s also meaningful and fulfilling in many ways” (P10)
“Kinakaya kasi lagging nagpapasalamat mga pasyente naming sa lahat ng gingawa naming for them” (It can be exhausting due to long hours, but it’s all worth it because our patients are always grateful for everything, we do for them.) (P11)
“Despite the stress, we find the job rewarding because we are helping patients live better lives.” (P12)

Theme 4: Structured Routines

The theme revealed that hemodialysis nurses go beyond simple tasks, as they voice:

“Reviewing patient charts. I do pre at post HD assessment, I monitor their vital signs, and I watch out any untoward events.” (P1)
“We do assessment, cannulation while we observe for any complications, provide patient education, and offer emotional support, all while promoting a safe and comfortable.” (P6)
“We closely monitor machines and patient conditions to prevent complications”. (P12)

“We’re constantly watching the machines and checking on our patients to make sure everything’s okay.” (P14)

“ang daming technical na kailangang matutunan, yung pag-handle ng machine, pag-tusok ng needles, monitoring, at pag-manage ng possible na complications. Pero habang tumatagal, nasanay din ako at nahanap ko ‘yung peak ko.” (There were so many technical things I needed to learn like handling the machine, inserting needles, monitoring, and managing possible complications. But as time went by, I got used to it and eventually found my peak.) (P15)

Theme 5: Patient-Centered Care

Participants reveal a profound commitment to patient-centered care, and their continued effort to address not only patients’ physical need but also their emotional and psychological challenges. As they reflected:

“I help them hold on to life a little longer, a little stronger.” (P1)

“We.... provide patient education, and offer emotional support, all while promoting a safe and comfortable.” (P6)

Theme 6: Sense of Purpose

A strong sense of purpose developed as a powerful driving force behind the commitment of nurses to hemodialysis care. Participants clearly expressed:

“I find purpose in the trust patients place in me” (P3)

“Becoming an HD nurse ay isa sa mga best decision ko so far.” (Becoming an HD nurse is one of the best decisions I've made so far) (P5)

“I truly felt more like a nurse when I became an HD nurse. I think it’s a calling in my profession to be here.” (P9)

“It can get really stressful, but honestly, it’s all worth it when you know you’re helping someone live a better, longer life. That’s what keeps me going.” (P14)

Theme 7: Deepened Nurse–Patient Relationship

The developed nurse-patient relationship reflects a holistic essence of patient-centered care for hemodialysis nurses, it’s a place where patients’ emotional, psychological, and social dimensions are acknowledged and nurtured.

“I know their stories, their struggles, and their small victories” (P1)

“the relationships we build through their regular treatments.” (P3)

“Theirs development of strong relationship with both patient and their families.” (P4)

“we build long-term relationships with our patients because we see them regularly, often multiple times a week.” (P7)

“I became more involved in direct patient care, developed stronger relationships with my patients.” (P9)

“Masaya sa HD, we share struggles and laughter in every session.” (P11)
“We often create strong bonds with our patients as we see them regularly in their treatment.” (P12)

Part 2. Memorable (Positive) Experience While Caring for a Hemodialysis Patient

Caring for hemodialysis patients is not only challenging but also deeply rewarding. Nurses often described their positive experiences as moments of growth, purpose, and affirmation of their role as caregivers. These experiences provided them with a sense of fulfillment, both personally and professionally, as they witnessed the impact of their care on patients' lives.

Theme 1: Moments of Personal and Professional Fulfillment

The theme captures the deeply meaningful experiences of hemodialysis nurse as they go on their duties.

“Truly enough rendering utmost care to them during treatment would save them from complication and even death, this made me a more responsible and caring nurse.” (P2)

“One unforgettable experience I had was the first time I successfully cannulated a fistula.” (P9)

“Yung may tiwala na sayo yung patient na ikaw ang tutusok o maglilinis ng mga access nila sobrang sarap sa pakiramdam na marinig na “ikaw nalang palagi magtusok sakin mas magaan kamay mo, ikaw nalang maglilis ng access ko ha mas maganda pagkaka close” it’s really fulfilling at ang saya para sakin na batang nurse.” (When a patient trusts you to be the one to insert the needle or clean their access, it feels so rewarding especially when they say things like, ‘Please be the one to insert the needle, your hand is lighter,’ or ‘Can you be the one to clean my access? You do it better.’ As a young nurse, it’s such a fulfilling and heartwarming feeling) (P14)

“may tiwala na saamin ang mga senior at mga pasyente namin pero ang masaya at the same time kase na she-share ko yung skills sa mga pasyenteng mas in need dito.” (It can be really stressful when the seniors and patients put their trust in me. But at the same time, it’s also rewarding because I get to share my skills with patients who need it the most) (P15)

Theme 2: Emotional Bonding Through Repeated Interaction

The strong bond that builds between hemodialysis nurse and their patient is largely shaped by the regularity and constancy of treatment they have. As for the participants:

“sa HD everyday, every week same patient lang ang hinahandle. So mapapalapit talaga yung loob ko sakanila.” (P5)

“He said he appreciated how we treated him like family.” (P10)

“Every birthday ng pasyente nagpapakain sila, they gave us foods tapos sabay sabay kaming kumain. Palagi silang grateful pagkatapos ng treatment.” (P11)

Theme 3: Leading by Example

Despite these challenges, many nurses achieve an ability for professional endurance and emotional resilience. As they expressed:

“Kahit na may sakit sila, kahit na nahihirapan sila sa kalagayan nula ay nagagawa pa din nilang maging positibo sa buhay. Dahil sa mga ito, natutunan ko sakanila na ppwede umiyak, pwede malungkot pero wag na wag sususko.” (Despite their illness at struggles they face; they still manage to stay positive in life. Because of them, I have learned that it’s okay to cry, to feel sad but never give up. In life, there will be unexpected problems that always come but what matter most is to keep fighting and never lose hope.) (P5)

“Sa kabila ng hirap, nananatili silang mahinahon at mapagpasalamat.” (Despite the challenges they face, they stay composed and thankful.) (P6)

Theme 4: Daily Gratitude as an Emotional Reward

The theme shows how daily gratitude can affect hemodialysis and can serve as a powerful reward that makes nurses go despite the physical, and emotional demands of their job. Participants shared:

“Every day is a memorable day..... because of the everyday smile of our CKD patients as they enter the Dialysis unit, saying their gratitude to us...” (P1)

“Salamat ma’am nadugtungan na naman ang buhay naming” Thank you, ma’am, you’ve given us more time to live (P2)

“they never forget to be grateful to is and it makes our heart happy and delightful.” (P7)

“bilang hemodialysis nurse ay kapag pinupuri o pinasasalamat ako ng mga pasyente ko. Simpleng ‘thank you’ man lang iyan ay napakalaking bagay na nito.” (As a hemodialysis nurse, when my patients compliment or thank me. Even a simple ‘thank you’ means a lot. It makes me feel that my efforts are appreciated) (P8)

“hindi ko makakalimutan ang pasyenteng palaging nagpapasalamat sa simpleng mga bagay na ginagawa namin hanggang sa pag-assist sa dialysis.” (I will never forget the patient who always expressed gratitude for the simple things we did, even just assisting with dialysis. Those words of thanks gave me strength and joy in my work.) (P13)

Part 3. Negative Experience While Caring for a Hemodialysis Patient

The complexity of the job demands competencies to respond in a life-threatening situation. Many aspects of hemodialysis nursing are rewarding, not every experience is satisfactory.

Theme 1: Struggles with Skill Gaps and Clinical Competence

Nurses shared challenges and struggles often led to feelings of anxiety, emotional exhaustion, and self-doubt in their competence.

“During my first few weeks, I had negative experiences on unsuccessful AVF cannulation.....Being rejected and causing someone’s distress is emotionally taxing.” (P2)

“when I struggled to properly initiate a hemodialysis treatment on my own..... This experience left me feeling frustrated and inadequate.” (P3)

“madalas akong makaranas ng emosyonal na pagod dahil sa haba ng oras ng trabaho at bigat ng responsibilidad.” (I often experience emotional exhaustion due to the long working hours and heavy responsibilities.) (P6)

“I’m still anxious to do some procedure and it seems that patients cannot trust me” (P7)

“May mga pasyente na naninibago saakin, they are scared to be taken care kasi nag aalangan sila saamin at humihiling na ibang staff.” (Some are scared to be taken care and even request other staff.) (P8)

Theme 2: Managing Difficult or Rude Patients

Nurses encounter rudeness and irritability from patients, often linked to the emotional burden of chronic illness. As they shared:

“Patients can be really rude sometimes I always try to remind myself, that they are sick people and sick people feel uncomfortable and irritated, that’s why they can be rude” (P1)

“Living with a chronic illness like CKD takes a lot of emotions patients become irritable” (P10)

Theme 3: Emotional Impact of Patient Death and Loss

The theme focuses on the emotional impact of healthcare personnel, especially hemodialysis nurses on how they feel when they face their patient death and loss.

“Ang negatibong karanasan na akong naranasan ay ang mamatayan ng pasyente na ang kasamang bantay ay ang kanyang anak. Nakaaapekto saakin ito bilang ako ay isang ina kasi sa murang edad ng batang naulila mahirap itong tanggapin.” (One of the most difficult experience I’ve had was losing a patient whose companion was her child. As a mother, it deeply affected me because for a child to lose a parent at such a young age is truly heartbreaking.) (P4)

“magugulat ka nalang na yung paspyenteng nakakakwentuhan at tawanan mo lang nung huling session niya ay namatay na.” (I’ve experienced is when you suddenly find out that a patient you were just laughing and chatting with during their last session has passed away.) (P5)

“may mga pasyente na biglang bumagsak ang kalagayan habang naka-dialysis at hindi na namin siya nailigtas. Personal na naapektuhan ako dahil matagal na namin siyang kasama” (There were times when a patient’s condition

suddenly worsened during dialysis, and we were unable to save them. Personally, it affected me deeply because we had been with that patient for a long time.) (P15)

Part 4. Significant Challenge that Hemodialysis Nurses Face on Daily Basis

Hemodialysis nurses encounter numerous daily challenges that test their skills, resilience, and emotional strength. From managing unpredictable, life-threatening complications to addressing patients' physical and emotional struggles, their work demands constant vigilance and adaptability.

Theme 1: Unpredictable and life-threatening of dialysis

The unpredictability and risk of sudden deterioration make their daily work emotionally and physically challenging.

“news will come up that a patient of ours died, it's like we are waiting for them because it's their scheduled day for their dialysis but then they won't come, we don't know if their just absent or something bad happened to them. (P1)

“biggest challenge I have faced in daily basis because they need a high risk of complications” (P2)

“there's always the possibility that a patient's condition could suddenly deteriorate.....patients who can experience life-threatening complications at any moment.” (P3)

“makita ang mga pasyente na nahihirapan pagdumadating at halos mangiyak iyak at sinasabing away na nila at nahihirapan na sila” (biggest challenges I face every day is seeing patients arrive in pain with tears, saying they want to give up.) (P4)

minsang kami rin yung nahihirapan kapag hindi okay yung pasyente naming during their treatment.” (When patients aren't doing well during treatment, it's often us nurses who have to manage the situation, which can be really tough.) (P9)

“Hindi maiwasang magkaroon ng untowards events during the four- five hours of HD treatment ng mga pasyente.” (Untoward events are sometimes unavoidable during the four to five hours of HD treatment) (P10)

“hindi naming alam kung anong mangyayari sa mga pasyente while having their treatment. Some may go home walking, and some may not finish treatment and unfortunately pass away.” (The uncertainty of what might happen to our patients during their treatment. So may go home walking and some may not finish treatment and unfortunately pass away.) (P12)

“Para sa akin, ang pinakamalaking hamon ay kapay may pasyenteng hindi na bumabalik lalo na kung matagal na naming kasama.” (For me, the biggest challenge is when a patient no longer returns, especially if we've been with them for a long time.) (P14)

“sa pagbabantay palang ng pasyente e may biglaan nalang magbabago sa kanilang kondisyon habang nakasalang. Minsan, bigla na lang babagsak ang blood pressure o mahihilo” (Even just monitoring the patient can be

unpredictable. Sometimes, their condition suddenly changes while undergoing dialysis like a sudden drop in blood pressure or dizziness.) (P15)

Theme 2: Shortage of Staff

The theme focuses on the inadequate HD nurse staffing which not only interferes with the proper delivery of care services to the patients but also can add to their workload and their well-being. Some participants shared:

“kapag kulang ang staff. Hindi kasi palaging kompleto kami dito, kaya kung minsan yung ratio naming e higit pa sa normal patient ratio.” (When we are short-staffed. We're not always fully staffed here, so sometimes our nurse-to-patient ratio is higher than usual.) (P8)

“May ibang pasyente na need ng mabilisang intervention..... kasi kung minsan iilan lang kaming nurses sa floor”. (Some patients suddenly require immediate intervention, which becomes a real challenge especially when there are only a few of us nurses on the floor.) (P10)

“Mahirap at nakakapagod ang trabaho, lalo na kapag minsan kulang sa staff.” (The job is hard and exhausting, especially when we're sometimes short on staff) (P13)

Theme 3: Suppress Personal Stress

The theme highlights the hidden dimension of occupational stress of hemodialysis nurses.

“matinding challenge ay ang paggising ng maaga yung pinakamahirap” (Biggest challenges for me is waking up early. But because I need to earn and have responsibilities) (P6)

“pinakamalaking hamon araw-araw ay ang pagpasok sa AM shift. Mahirap gumising ng maaga lalo na kapag pagod pa mula sa nakaraang araw.” (The biggest challenge I face every day is reporting for the AM shift. It's difficult to wake up early, especially when I'm still tired from the previous day.) (P7)

Theme 4: Technical and Operational Challenges

Hemodialysis nurses often deal with a number of operational and technical challenges that affect the standard and continuity of care. As participants emphasized:

“...and machines need to be operated with enough proficiency.” (P2)

“Isa sa mga challenge saamin kapag may pasyenteng toxic, kasi hindi naman daily yung rounds ng mga doctor”

(One of the challenges we face is dealing with toxic or difficult patients, especially since their doctors don't do daily rounds.) (P9)

Part 5: Perception of Hemodialysis Nurses in Hemodialysis Care

Hemodialysis nurses view their role as vital in sustaining the lives of patients with chronic kidney disease. They perceive their work as both a responsibility and a calling, balancing technical expertise with compassion.

Theme 1: Deepened Understanding of Holistic and Compassionate Care

The theme captures how nurses move beyond tasks and responsibilities to be more integrated with patient-centered care.

“the essence of being a nurse won’t fade and will always be there, the passion, the care and the love to our profession.” (P1)

“Working with HD patient taught me to be more careful, watchful, and mindful.” (P2)

“Working as a hemodialysis nurse has transformed my understanding of patient care by highlighting the importance of compassion, patience, and emotional support..... This experience has taught me that effective care goes beyond treatment it requires recognizing the strength patients show every day” (P3)

“Binago ng pagiging HD nurse ko na kailangang mas maging maintindihin, mas palawaking ko ang pag-unawa at pasenysa” (Becoming an HD nurse has changed me, it taught me to be more understanding, to expand my patience and compassion) (P4)

“yung isang perception na natutunan ko din when it comes to giving patient care ay just being there for them” (One valuable perception I’ve had when it comes to patient care is that sometimes, just being there for them truly makes a difference) (P5)

“HD nurses has transformed my perspective on patient care, illness and resilience by allowing me to provide with deeper compassion and helping me provide more effective and meaningful care.” (P10)

“Mas naging lumalim ang pag-unawa ko sa tunay na kahulugan care” (My understanding of the true meaning of care has deepened.) (P11)

“Mas nailapit ko ang sarili ko sa mga pasyente at mas naiintindihan ko na ang hirap ng mga pasyente ngayon” (“I’ve become closer to the patients and I now understand more deeply the hardships they go through) (P13)

“I’ve learned that healing isn’t always about curing. Sometimes it’s just about making patients feel safe, comfortable, and heard.” (P14)

“Working in hemodialysis taught me the value of consistency and emotional presence..... they need someone who shows up for them regularly, someone who listens and reassures them. (P15)

Theme 2: Admiration for Patient Resilience and Strength

The following statements highlight how nurses are deeply impacted by the unwavering spirit of those they serve.

“living with an illness takes daily courage and resilience.” (P8)

“Their strength and positivity remind me to stay grateful and do my best every day.” (P9)

Theme 3: Heightened Appreciation for Personal Health and Preventive Care

The data gathered revealed participants found a sense of urgency in valuing their health as they affiliated in a hemodialysis setting.

“narealize ko rin na dapat pahalagahan ang sariling kalusugan habang maaga pa”. (I’ve come to realize how important it is to take care of my health while I still can) (P6)

“Narealize ko na lahat ng ating action ay may consequences that’s why we need to have a healthy lifestyle.” (I realized that every action we take has consequences, which is why it's so important to live a healthy lifestyle) (P7)

Part 6. The Coping Mechanisms or Support Systems of Hemodialysis Nurses

The theme highlights the strong interpersonal relationships that built and the supportive culture they have which plays an important role in helping nurses manage their challenges, personal stress and to find sense of belongingness.

Theme 1: Peer Connection and Workplace Camaraderie

Hemodialysis nurses echoed that the friendship they build in their co – works or within the dialysis unit serves as an emotional anchor to each of them.

“I try talking openly with my coworkers to create a supportive environment” (P3)

“Its always my friends at work who have the same experiences as mine, that why its nice to have them around because they make me smile whenever I felt overwhelmed at work.” (P7)

“Isa sa mga coping mechanism ko kapag stress ay eating foods with my co – workers” (One of my coping mechanisms when I'm stressed is eating with my co-workers) (P9)

“I bond with my co-workers during breaks” (P11)

“build camaraderie among staff” (P12)

Theme 2: Emotional reliance on family and close friends

Beyond the workplace, hemodialysis nurse finds emotional strength through their loved one, their family and close friends

“spending time with family and friends” (P3)

“lagi kong nagiging support system ay ang aking pamilya mga kaibigan.” (Whenever I feel stressed whether from work or personal matters are my family and friends who are there to support) (P6)

“spending time with family also helps a lot.” (P11)

Theme 3: Personal Coping Rituals and Self-Care Practices

Participants shared various self-care habits that helped them decompress and sustain emotional resilience.

“I still play games... either mobile or PC” (P1)

“praying and taking some deep breaths. I get nutritious meal and listening to relaxing music” (P2)

“I also try to prioritize rest and healthy habits outside of work, such as exercise” (P3)

“Whenever I felt stress I do self-care, regular exercise, meditation and hobbies that help reduce it.” (P10)

Self-reflection lang talaga ang ginagawa ko lalo na pag may nag toxic sa duty or nag text na expired na yung patient” (I usually just reflect quietly, especially when something toxic happens during duty or when I receive a message that a patient has passed away) (P13)

“Prayer and spirituality play a big role in helping me cope. Taking time to pray or meditate gives me peace of mind and strength to face difficult days at work” (P15)

Part 7. Meaningful Rewards and Career Fulfillment in Hemodialysis Nursing

Hemodialysis nurses find deep fulfillment in their work through the daily expressions of gratitude and appreciation from patients.

Theme 1: Daily Expressions of Gratitude Uplift Nurses

Even little acts of gratitude from patients can make a big difference in the emotionally and physically taxing area of hemodialysis care.

“It’s the patients smile and gratitude moments that is rewarding for me... Whenever they see me/us, they thank us for everything. It makes me feel so fulfilled as nurse and despite the tiring shifts and low paid salary, everything feels so worth it when they show such gratitude.” (P1)

“Moments when patients express gratitude or show improvement remind me that my work truly matters.” (P3)

“ang makita ang mga ngiti ng mga pasyente kapag nag uumpisa at matatapos ang kanilang session. Ang sarap sa pakiramdam” (Most rewarding aspect of my work as an HD nurse is seeing the smiles of patients at the start and end of their sessions. It feels incredibly fulfilling) (P4)

“When they were so grateful in all matters that we did to them, that’s greatly contributes to my career satisfaction” (P6)

“seeing our patients express genuine gratitude and appreciation for what we do. Even small gestures like a reassuring smile, it really means for me” (P7)

“ang mga simpleng regalo at pasasalamat mula sa mga pasyente.” (The small gifts and words of gratitude from patients) (P8)

“when they greet us ‘good morning/good afternoon’, or just smile during their treatment makes a big impact to me.” (P9)

"Its fulfilling in every after-session when patients are grateful on the things" (P10)

"Even a simple 'thank you' means so much" (P11)

"Their simple thank you and smiles when they leave the units is the best reward for me." (P12)

"Siguro yung uuwi silang naka ngiti at masaya... makikita mo silang naka ngiti at tumatawa sobrang sarap na pakiramdam na yung simpleng pag-upo mo sa tabi nila eh ang laking bagay na para sakanila yun" (When they go home smiling and happy... you see them smiling and laughing. It feels so fulfilling to know that just sitting beside them already means so much to them.) (P13)

"Seeing them leave the unit with a smile, or hearing them say, 'Thank you' gives me a deep sense of connection. These moments remind me that nursing is more than just a job, it's a calling." (P15)

Theme 2: Strong Nurse-Patient Bonds Develop Over Time

One of the most unique and rewarding aspects as a hemodialysis nurse is the chance to form a lasting and meaningful relationship with patients.

"working with hemodialysis patients are the meaningful relationships I build with them and the visible impact of my care on their well-being. Being part of their ongoing health journey... gives me a strong sense of purpose" (P3)

"sobrang fulfilling at rewarding din naman kasi you get to know your patient more and more." (It's also incredibly fulfilling and rewarding because you get to know your patients more and more over time) (P5)

"patients share their foods, they even celebrate their birthday with us" (P9)

"knowing that you are a source of hope and comfort during a very difficult time in their lives." (P14)

Part 8. The Support or Resources they Wish are Readily Available to Hemodialysis Nurses' Workplace

Hemodialysis nurses emphasized the need for more staff, emotional support, adequate equipment, and continuous training. These resources would help reduce stress, prevent burnout, and improve patient care.

Theme 1: Adequate Staffing and Manpower

Nurses emphasized the urgent need for sufficient staffing and support personnel in hemodialysis units. They highlighted that inadequate manpower leads to stress, burnout, and compromised care delivery. In their words:

"proper trained renal technician is a must in having hemodialysis unit and they should be the one taking care of machines...., I wish we have sufficient manpower to distribute to avoid too much stress to the team" (P1)

“I wish for additional HD nurses, dialysis technician. And I think we also need administrative and records personnel... there is a steady physician on duty” (P2)

“Sana mayroong suporta para madagdagana ang mga HD nurse” (I hope they'll add HD nurses) (P4)

“Magkaroon sana ng mas tamang staffing at dagdagan ang mga HD nurse para maiwasan ang burnout at work overload” (There should be proper staffing and more hemodialysis nurses to help prevent burnout and work overload.) (P8)

“kulang tayo sa resources, like sa additional nursing staff” (We often lack resources, such as additional nursing staff) (P11)

“We need a Physician on Duty (POD) that will really stay inside the unit to regularly check our patient situation” (P12)

“I hope there will be enough staff for every shift. Sometimes we are understaffed, yet there are many patients to care for” (P14)

Theme 2: Emotional and Mental Health Support

Nurses stressed the need for counseling, peer support, moral encouragement, and time to rest as vital for coping with stress and emotional fatigue. Participants shared:

“I wish there were more readily available... emotional support... having structured emotional support, such as counseling or peer support groups, would help nurses cope with the stress and emotional toll that comes with caring for chronically ill patients” (P3)

“I hope there were more emotional support resources available for hemodialysis nurses due to our nature of work.” (P6)

“Sana ay magkaroon man lang ng emotional support para sa mga hemodialysis nurse, tulad ng counseling at moral support.” (I hope emotional support will also be provided to hemodialysis nurses, such as counseling and moral support.) (P7)

“Kahit manlang magkaroon kami ng bakasyon to unwind para makapag pahinga, makapag -recharged kasi mabigat rin yung work namin.” (I hope there would be more opportunities for vacation or time off to unwind. Havi ng time to rest and recharge is important for our mental and emotional well-being, especially in such a demanding role) (P9)

“I wish there were more mental health support programs for nurses. Every day we face high levels of stress, pressure, and emotional fatigue.” (P13)

Theme 3: Equipment, Supplies, and Infrastructure

This theme reflects the nurses' concerns about limited space, inadequate equipment, and insufficient resources in the hemodialysis unit. They emphasized that these shortages affect both efficiency and quality of patient care. As they said:

“I wish it is wider for us to move more freely and efficiently, our unit now is too small for its current patient number catering” (P1)

“Sana madagdagan ang mga equipments dahil hindi sapat ang isang droplight lang” (I hope more equipment can be provided, because having just one droplight is not enough) (P5)

“kulang tayo sa equipment kaya we tend to do DIY para mas convenient sa mga pasyente naming” (We often lack resources, such equipment. Sometimes, we have to improvise just to make things more convenient for our patients.) (P11)

Theme 4: Continuous Training and Professional Growth

Hemodialysis nurses emphasize the importance of continuous training, seminars, and peer support to enhance their skills, confidence, and professional growth. As they said:

“Access to regular, updated training programs would improve our skills and confidence in handling complex situations.” (P3)

“sana mga seminars para continuous pa rin yung knowledge and magkaroon ng professional growt” (I also hope for more seminars and training opportunities to support continuous learning and professional growth.) (P8)

“There should be peer support, regular meetings for nurses where we can openly share our challenges, experiences, and suggestions” (P10)

“I wish and hope for regular training and seminars so we can stay up to date with new protocols and technologies” (P15)

DISCUSSION

This section presents a comprehensive interpretation of the finding derives from the lived experienced of hemodialysis nurses. Drawing from the narratives of the participants, key themes emerged that describe their general experiences in the clinical setting. These are further substantiated and contextualized using relevant literature. The discussion is organized according to the specific research questions.

I. General Experiences of Nurses in Caring Hemodialysis Patients

The themes reflect the multiple aspects of hemodialysis care, emphasizing the physical and mental obstacles that nurses experience daily. The lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses are shaped by a complex interplay of technical responsibilities, emotional resilience, and deep human connection. Their experiences are defined not only by clinical tasks but also by the deep interpersonal relationships they form with their patients, who often receive treatment for years.

The following themes emerged from the data: (1) Complex Demands of Hemodialysis Nursing, (2) Technical Expertise in Hemodialysis Nursing, (3) Resiliency Amidst Meaningful Cares, (4) Structured Routines, (5) Patient-Centered Care, (6) Sense

of Purpose, and (7) Deepened Nurse–Patient Relationship. These themes offer insight into the day-to-day challenges and rewards associated with this specialized area of practice.

Participants consistently described hemodialysis nursing as physically exhausting and emotionally demanding. The long shifts, continuous patient interaction, and responsibility for critically ill individuals contributed to fatigue and burnout. This aligns with the findings of the study of Kersten et al. (2020), nurses working in dialysis units face complex and demanding working conditions. The finding of the study reveals the work tasks include prolonged and close contact with chronically ill, confrontation with the suffering and death of patients and the use of complex technology. The participants recognized the complex nature of dialysis care, from its intensity and repetitiveness, they are expected to provide technically precise care to the same patient's multiple times a week, often for several hours per session. This repetitive, high-stakes environment fosters both routine fatigue and long-term psychological weariness.

The participants also emphasized that technical competency is central to their role. On top of the physical exhaustion, the demands of duties constantly challenge the nurses' professional competence and emotional resilience. Moreover, operating and troubleshooting complex dialysis machines, performing accurate vascular access, and responding to alarms are routine tasks that demand focused attention and constant vigilance to ensure patient safety and treatment efficacy.

According to the study by Lee, et.al, (2022), It is necessary for nurses to become accustomed to operating complex HD machines, handling various alarm systems, and performing dialysis. Therefore, mastering these skills ensures both patient safety as well as efficiency of care delivery. Hemodialysis nurse shared that their duties frequently begin with the preparation and calibration of dialysis machines which requires focus and attention. A significant challenge for nurses as dialysis continues, sometimes technical errors and alarms come as expected. Nurses are expected to manage sophisticated and complex machines that both requiring technical expertise and hands-on experience. Nurses face various mechanical problems with HD machines and resolving these is one of their main tasks. Additionally, Lee et.al (2022) asserted that it is necessary for nurses to become accustomed to operating complex HD machines, handling various alarm systems, and performing dialysis. Moreover, Kersten et al. (2020) emphasized hemodialysis work environment is highly technical, with nurses needing to master complex hemodialysis equipment to provide safe, efficient, and effective care to patients. Hemodialysis nurses are required to fulfil many demanding roles such as advocate, caregiver, educator, mentor, and technician while patients attend a dialysis unit. In this regard, technical expertise is a core dimension of professional competency in hemodialysis care.

Despite the stress and emotional toll of caring for patients undergoing life-sustaining treatment, hemodialysis nurses found meaning in their work. In the study conducted by Kim et.al (2022), resilience is a positive concept that allows nurses to overcome stressful situations and to adapt positively, resulting in the maintenance of their

psychological well-being and mental health. Even though working in a high-pressure clinical setting, nurses find strength in the meaning and fulfillment they get from caring for patients who are undergoing life-sustaining treatment. Similar results were reported in the research of Cooper et al. (2020), that nurse resilience contains a complex and dynamic process that changes over time and according to the situation. Embodying not only personal attributes but also external resources. Nurses in this study reflected this dynamic by adapting positively to stress and adversity, guided by dedication and appreciation from their patients. This underscores the concept that resilience in nursing is not merely about endurance but is deeply rooted in emotional rewards also to transforming challenges into a source of purpose and fulfillment in their profession. Therefore, the expressions of gratitude from patients, the perceived impact of their care, and their commitment to serve served as powerful motivators.

Participants also highlighted the importance of structured daily routines, which guide the sequential tasks from machine preparation to patient monitoring and education. As highlighted in the study by Nazly et. al. (2021), nurses at hemodialysis units have care protocols that include vital signs, patient weight before and after dialysis, assessment of vascular access, and monitoring of the basic metabolic panel. As they begin each shift by preparing and calibrating each machine and familiarizing themselves with patient histories, these tasks can help in reducing errors and ensuring consistent quality of care. After preparation, hemodialysis nurses perform cannulations of fistulas while ensuring aseptically techniques. Initiation of treatment began, as they concurrently observed for clinical complications or mechanical problems, patient education, and emotional support which exemplifies the multifaced nature of hemodialysis care. Therefore, these routines provided a sense of order and control, particularly in high-stress settings, while supporting clinical accuracy and safety. In this study, routines were not viewed as repetitive but rather as necessary frameworks that support the delivery of complex, consistent care.

The study also reveals that participants demonstrated a deep commitment to patient-centered care, emphasizing the importance of addressing not only the physiological needs of patients but also their emotional and psychological well-being. Their care approach involves not only the delivery of medical interventions, but also emotional and psychosocial support tailored to the unique needs of each patient. The research conducted by Hayes et al. (2021) also reflects this perspective, stating that the ability to provide holistic, respectful, patient-centered care, along with a level of empathy, was highlighted as the qualities required to provide good care to patients receiving hemodialysis. In the study, nurses described providing emotional support, patient education, and building therapeutic relationships as integral parts of their role. By supporting patients holistically through empathy and compassion, as hemodialysis nurses, they act as anchors in their patients' health journey. The care they render exemplifies relational nursing where empathy, communication, and continuity are key to improving patient outcomes and satisfaction.

Moreover, from the findings obtained, a strong sense of purpose was a recurring sentiment among participants. Captured the emotional bond nurses have with their work and the satisfaction they get from earning patients' trust and having a significant influence

on their daily lives. As a result, this theme reflects how their daily interactions with patients and the impact of their care contribute to a deep-seated feeling of fulfillment, motivation, and professional identity. This supports the evidence presented by Cabrera-Aguilar et al. (2023), that finding meaning and purpose in one's work can serve as a protective factor against burnout and enhance emotional resilience. This is also aligned with the study of Yamamoto et al. (2024), that when nurses feel that their work has a profound impact and contributes to the well-being of others, it can provide a sense of purpose and motivation that helps them persevere through challenging situations. Furthermore, many participants viewed their role as a calling, expressing fulfillment in knowing that their work directly contributed to improving and extending patients' lives. As highlighted in the study by Kallio et al. (2022), calling has been a common reason for people entering the nursing profession. Having a calling has been found to boost nurses' work motivation, job satisfaction, and work engagement. The trust bestowed upon them by their patients further reinforced this professional identity. Over time, emotional bonds form with patients and hemodialysis nurses as they see each other two or three times a week. As day goes by, they form emotional bonds just like family which some participants emphasized as a core source of motivation and personal connection. Emotional connection captures the deep relationship inherent in hemodialysis care. Hemodialysis nurses do not merely perform an efficient task, but they also develop meaningful, familial relationships with their patients which significantly reinforce the sense of purpose and emotional attachment in their role as hemodialysis nurses.

Likewise, due to the frequency and duration of hemodialysis sessions, hemodialysis nurses reported developing familial-like bonds with their patients. These relationships were described as mutually beneficial, offering emotional support for both nurses and patients while improving the quality of care. The participants in this study affirmed that these relationships are not only a natural outcome of chronic care but are also central to their motivation and sense of professional fulfillment. The data revealed that hemodialysis nurses build strong connections with their patients with their patients driven by the continuous and on hand care in dialysis care. Given that end-stage renal disease is a chronic condition and treatment is performed multiple times a week, nurses frequently interact with patients, which creates a sense of familiarity and intimacy. Over time, this frequent interaction and continued care form a meaningful, familial relationship, mutual trust, and a shared journey throughout their treatment which leads to a unique therapeutic bond that extends beyond clinical duties. These bonds become deeply personal as nurses describe their patients as "family" which contributes to patient well-being. The developed nurse-patient relationship reflects a holistic essence of patient-centered care for hemodialysis nurses, it's a place where patients' emotional, psychological, and social dimensions are acknowledged and nurtured. This aligns with the study conducted by Camedda et al. (2023), nurses themselves report deriving personal satisfaction from these relationships. The study noted that "becoming attached to chronic patients" contributed significantly to nurses' personal and job satisfaction. In conclusion, the findings emphasize the importance of long-term nurse-patient relationships in hemodialysis care, as they provide a vital source of strength, healing, and resilience for patients and nurses navigating the challenges of chronic illness together. These relationships serve as the foundation for holistic, patient-centered practice.

II. Memorable or Positive Experiences of Nurses in Caring Hemodialysis Patients

Hemodialysis nurses encounter not only clinical challenges but also profoundly meaningful experiences that leave lasting impressions on their emotional and professional lives. These lived experiences reflect moments of fulfillment, gratitude, resilience, and personal transformation. In examining the lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses, several key themes emerged that reflect the emotional, relational, and professional dimensions of their roles.

The following themes emerged from the data: (1) Moments of Personal and Professional Fulfillment, (2) Emotional Bonding Through Repeated Interaction, (3) Leading by Example, and (4) Daily Gratitude as an Emotional Reward. These themes highlight the emotional, relational, and professional rewards that contribute to the nurses' sustained motivation, satisfaction, and resilience in the demanding field of hemodialysis care.

Participants consistently highlighted moments in their practice where they felt competent, confident, and deeply fulfilled. The theme captures the deeply meaningful experiences of hemodialysis nurse as they go on their duties. Their instances in their work felt a heightened sense of purpose, responsibility, and growth in their role as caregivers. Being a hemodialysis nurse is difficult as they say, but the positive impact outcomes are immeasurable. Nurses in hemodialysis care were able to demonstrate clinical competencies such as successfully performing complex tasks like cannulation of AVF, troubleshooting machines on a mid-session, fluid management as well as proficiency in documentation, attention to detail, and adherence to safety protocols. These competencies were not only a technical milestone but also a significant confidence booster. These clinical achievements were perceived as milestones that validated their growth as nurses and reinforced their sense of capability. These rewarding experiences contributed to the nurses' continuous development on both a personal and professional level. These positive experiences increased their emotional commitment to their work and validated their clinical skills, which improved job satisfaction and the quality of care delivered.

One of the most defining aspects of dialysis care is the frequency and continuity of patient-nurse interaction. Participants described how regular engagement created space for emotional bonding, where relationships evolved from purely professional to profoundly personal. These repeated contacts fostered mutual trust, familiarity, and understanding, transforming care into a shared journey. As for the participants, patients often express appreciation and trust which furthers the nurses' sense of fulfillment and purpose. Several participants emphasized that as family-like dynamics that form in the clinical setting. Where patient starts to see nurses as an emotional support system in addition to professionals. These bonds are further strengthened through shared experiences like celebrating patient milestones, offering comforts during difficult sessions, or just having regular conversations to further solidify these ties. These can be a small moment for some but for hemodialysis nurses, it can create a foundation of trust and emotional safety. These findings echo the conclusions of Molina-Mula et. al. (2020)

emphasized that having a solid relationship manifested by hemodialysis nurses is a support system and provides the nurse with good psychological well-being. In addition, the emotional bonding fostered through repeated interactions serves as a cornerstone of hemodialysis nursing care. It goes beyond routine medical tasks, transforming the nurse-patient relationship into a therapeutic alliance rooted in empathy, mutual respect, and shared humanity.

Participants also shared how their patients' strength and perseverance became sources of personal inspiration. Witnessing patients endure chronic illness with dignity and optimism prompted nurses to reflect on their attitudes toward adversity. In the emotionally demanding environment of hemodialysis care, nurses frequently witness and are exposed to the physical suffering of their patients, emotional pain, and the psychological burden they feel. Despite these challenges, many nurses achieve an ability for professional endurance and emotional resilience. In the study, a significant contributor to the nurse-patient relationship was nurses not only give care but also receive strength from their patients. Thereby, it shows how hemodialysis nurses internalize the strength, perseverance, and hope of their patients in the everyday challenges they face. Where nurses develop resilience when they are repeatedly exposed to patients who, despite the chronicity of their condition, remain positive and have a will to live. In this study, hemodialysis nurses are moved and inspired by seeing first-hand how their patients overcome difficulties. Nurses begin to embody the peace, gratitude, and determination they usually witness in their patients, which shapes their emotional and professional attitudes. Through witnessing this unwavering spirit, hemodialysis nurses learned that accepting pain, expressing emotions, and continuing to push forward are not indications of weakness, but rather demonstrations of true strength.

Moreover, challenges at work cannot be removed, despite the challenges of waking in hemodialysis care, hemodialysis nurses often find strength and motivation through their patients. They say, one of the most vital, yet often intangible benefits that hemodialysis nurses experience is the daily expression of gratitude from their patients. Simple acts of appreciation such as acknowledgment or appreciation, smiles, and words of thanks were found to be effective emotional reinforcements that helped nurses maintain their motivation and emotional well-being. These moments bring joy and emotional fulfillment making their hard work as a hemodialysis nurse worthwhile. Therefore, the theme shows how daily gratitude can affect hemodialysis and can serve as a powerful reward that makes nurses go despite the physical, and emotional demands of their job. According to Hermann (2023), the benefits of gratitude in practice can lead to better stress management, greater optimism, increased self-esteem, increased resilience, and better work relationships. Findings shows that patient gratitude becomes a sustaining force. It reaffirms the hemodialysis nurse's role as a caring compassionate provider to their patients during their life-sustaining health journey. Wherein the impact of nursing care rendered becomes heartfelt and enhances the nurse's sense of purpose and job fulfillment. This cycle is emotionally sustaining and integral to nurse resilience and retention. In this manner, the emotional rewards of cultivating gratefulness each day foster resilience, satisfaction at work, and a stronger dedication to patient-centered care.

III. Negative Experiences of the Nurses in Caring Hemodialysis Patients

While hemodialysis nursing offers meaningful professional and emotional rewards, it is also accompanied by significant challenges and difficult moments that hemodialysis nurses experience while caring for patients. Although their work is often meaningful, it also involves emotional strain, high expectations, and patient-related stress. The following themes emerged from the data and reflected the difficult realities of hemodialysis nursing: (1) Struggles with Skill Gaps and Clinical Competence, (2) Managing Difficult or Rude Patients, and (3) Emotional Impact on the patient.

In the study, many nurses shared that performing technical procedures in hemodialysis, such as cannulating AV fistulas or managing machine alarms, can be very challenging, especially for those who are new to the field. In the study of Staaf et al. (2022), emphasized that nurses have a great responsibility in the daily care of arteriovenous fistulae, which entails the potential to affect patency. However, good cannulation technique involves more than placing a needle in the vessel and relies on different skills to facilitate needling. Even with two to three months of training, they often felt unprepared when faced with complicated or emergency situations. These experiences sometimes led to failure, patient distrust, and feelings of frustration or inadequacy. For some participants, most probably those HD nurses who are more than 6 months in the field experience moments of failure such as unsuccessful AVF cannulation, distrust from patients, and even difficulties in initiating treatment that leads to low self-esteem, frustration, and exhaustion. However, not all experiences are positive. Hemodialysis nurses learned from these negative experiences. These findings showed the importance of continued support, mentoring, and additional training to help nurses grow professionally and emotionally.

In hemodialysis care, not all interactions are easy or positive. Nurses somehow encounter a patient who displays difficult behavior, and it is important to recognize that these "difficult behaviors" may be due to underlying psychosocial or medical issues. Huang et al. (2020) highlighted that repeated exposure to verbal abuse or non-cooperative attitudes can lead to emotional detachment and reduced empathy in nurses over time. Due to recurring and long-term dialysis treatment, patients become stressed or frustrated rooted in the emotional and physical toll of living with CKD which may manifest an uncooperative attitude, anxiety, and discomfort. Despite their difficult behavior, hemodialysis nurses bear with their attitude and remain patient or understanding of the present behaviors of these patients. In high-contact environments like dialysis units, this relational strain can compromise both the quality of care and nurse-patient rapport. Another recurring challenge that hemodialysis nurses face is managing difficult or rude patients. This theme highlights the emotional resilience and communication skills of hemodialysis nurses to maintain compassionate care in facing the behavioral challenges of their patients with chronic kidney disease undergoing a life-sustaining treatment. Moreover, Ahn et al. (2021) noted that such negative patient behaviors are a major contributor to occupational stress, burnout, and decreased job satisfaction among nurses. Hemodialysis nurse must have empathy, emotional intelligence, and patience to understand that the rudeness of their patient is not personal

but often rooted in their suffering, fear, and pain while undergoing hemodialysis treatment. Nurses should be empowered by doing all of these, by managing challenging interactions while maintaining high-quality care with compassion for their patients.

Nurses in this study also talked about how emotionally painful it is to lose a patient. Because hemodialysis patients come in two to three times a week, nurses form strong bonds with them, often seeing them like family. When a patient suddenly dies or deteriorates during treatment, the emotional impact can be deep and lasting. These experiences show the vulnerability of nurses. Hemodialysis nurse expressed their experiences and how affect their deep emotions when they are losing patients while on their treatment. Nurses voiced that when a patient suddenly deteriorates or passes away, it leaves a lasting emotional impact because they treat their patients as family. Some nurses recall some moments of loss that deeply affect them especially when a patient suddenly dies during their treatment witnessing firsthand or dies unexpectedly. These lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses are a manifestation that nurses relate personally to the situations. It reveals that the nurses have their vulnerability in the face of patient mortality and how their role extends beyond physical care. Hemodialysis nurses encompass genuine emotional connection that cannot be paid by their salary, every loss of a patient is deeply personal to them. The emotional demands of being a nurse underscore the importance of holistic support measures for nurses dealing with patient mortality.

IV. Challenges Experienced by the Nurses in Caring Hemodialysis Patients

The research further reveals that nurses' experience in the hemodialysis department revealed a complex and emotionally taxing environment. They shared that their work is not only technically demanding but also emotionally taxing, as they deal with life-threatening situations, limited resources, and personal sacrifices. The data revealed four key themes representing the challenges faced by nurses on a daily basis: (1) Unpredictability and Life-Threatening Nature of Dialysis, (2) Shortage of Staff, (3) Suppression of Personal Stress, and (4) Technical and Operational Challenges.

Each day is not the same for hemodialysis nurses as they deal with the unpredictable and critical care they deliver. The ongoing risk of patients deteriorating or even death is possible each day. Sometimes, their patient appears to be stable but can suddenly and unexpectedly experience severe complications before, during, and after their session. This is how hemodialysis treatment can go beyond each day. The treatment typically lasts for four to five hours, and every second lasts for each patient; the instability challenges the nurse's technical competence and emergency response and heavily affects them emotionally. As nurses expressed, many patients arrived at their setting stable, some visibly suffering with tears and expressing a desire to give up due to fatigue, pain, irritation, and emotional burden due to their chronic condition. Even the unexpected absence of their long-term patient warms the hemodialysis nurse that some might happen to them at home or on the way to their treatment. The sudden loss of patients leaves nurses in grief as they form emotional bonds with their patients especially when the loss happens without warning or notice. Moreover, the emotional impact of losing

patients, especially those with whom strong bonds were formed over time, further compounds the unpredictability. The participants expressed those sudden absences or deaths of long-term patients often led to unanticipated grief, underscoring the emotional toll of the job. The burden of emotional responsibility challenges nurses to remain composed, resilient, and competent, often with little time to process their emotional reactions. This approach is supported by the study of Babapour et al. (2022), that the responsibilities of, handling emergencies, and high expectations, excessive responsibility, and maintaining strict treatment protocols significantly contribute to occupational stress and burnout among nurses.

Another recurring concern among participants in the study was the inadequate nurse-to-patient ratio in hemodialysis units. With the increasing number of patients requiring dialysis, particularly in rural areas like Roxas, Isabela, many nurses are stretched beyond capacity. This staffing gap not only increases workload and fatigue but also compromises patient safety. Some participants shared how nurse-to-patient ratios often exceed the recommended levels where nurses are forced to manage more patients than they can and forced to have overtime extending at night to attend on-call hemodialysis treatment. The patient load and burden place hemodialysis nurses in a difficult position. The attention needed for just one patient is sub-divided due to a shortage of nurses. These circumstances put a high level of load on nurses, who must fulfill several responsibilities while providing care for numerous patients simultaneously. Participants described situations where emergency interventions were delayed or where the quality of patient care suffered due to the overwhelming responsibilities handled by too few nurses. The emotional and physical strain of these conditions contributes to burnout, decreases job satisfaction, and may ultimately lead to staff turnover. These challenges of nurses physically and emotionally are clearly evident as they mention that their work becomes more exhausting and harder when few nurses are on the floor. Burnout and mental fatigue are reflected on their faces as they express their feeling of being overworked. In conclusion, the theme highlights how the shortage of staff leads to ripple effects that compromise patient care, inadequate response to emergency situations, and how nurses feel physical, and emotional strain as they work on a daily basis. It draws attention to how essential adequate staffing is and how better support systems are needed in hemodialysis settings to guarantee patient safety and nurse well-being.

In the context of hemodialysis care, nurses are focused on clinical challenges and patient health outcomes after treatment. However, the findings of the study reveal that personal challenges are often overlooked in the aspect of nurse's live experiences. The theme highlights the hidden dimension of occupational stress of hemodialysis nurses. The pressure they manage personally, the fatigue they feel to meet the standards of their professions, and the personal needs that are suppressed due to the heavy responsibilities they take. Nurses described how they often pushed through fatigue, emotional discomfort, and even personal struggles to fulfill their duties. Many felt compelled to prioritize patient care over their well-being, reporting to work even when emotionally or physically drained. Participants shared how they fulfill their roles as hemodialysis nurses in a matter of sacrifice. Nurses begin their work early and end their shift in so-called "on-call". The strain of working an early shift and going home late is a significant challenge to them. The

verbatim of the patient reveal that despite the fatigue and demands of work, nurses continue to report for duty on time. They keep prioritizing their patient over their own recovery. Even when they are suppressed by physical and emotional discomfort, nurses still show up, they have this sense of sacrifice that is evident in the culture of Filipino healthcare workers that often places professional responsibility above personal health.

On the other hand of the present study, the operational structure of many dialysis units presents challenges, particularly the inconsistent presence of attending physicians. Hemodialysis nurses often deal with a number of operational and technical challenges that affect the standard and continuity of care. These difficulties frequently call for a high level of skill, prompt decision-making, and flexibility. An operational difficulty arises is the limited presence of physicians on duty in the unit. This absence becomes more challenging when dealing with "toxic" or critically ill people. Moreover, operating dialysis machines requires technical competencies as they can malfunction at times during the treatment. As Mohammed et al. (2021) emphasize, system-level inefficiencies in healthcare settings can directly impact both nurse performance and patient safety. Nurses are often left to manage complex cases on their own or wait for delayed decisions, especially in emergencies. This operational gap can heighten anxiety and create moral distress among nurses who feel responsible but unsupported. Participant narratives revealed that these challenges are not only practical in nature but also psychological, as the responsibility for patient outcomes often falls disproportionately on the nurses. These challenges or difficulties experienced by hemodialysis nurses emphasize how crucial it is for staff members to be able to troubleshoot quickly and efficiently in order to maintain care continuity and safety.

V. Ways on How Hemodialysis Nurse Changed their Perception of Patient Care, Chronic Illness and Resilience

The findings revealed that hemodialysis nurses, through close interactions with patients, developed profound insights into holistic care, personal health, and the resilience of the human spirit. Three central themes emerged: (1) Deepened Understanding of Holistic and Compassionate Care, (2) Admiration for Patient Resilience and Strength, and (3) Heightened Appreciation for Personal Health and Preventive Care. These themes illustrate the personal and professional transformations that occur in the dialysis setting, enriching nurses' sense of purpose and commitment.

Hemodialysis nurses reported a significant shift in their approach to care from primarily task-based routines to a more holistic and relational model. Participants emphasized becoming more careful, watchful, and mindful recognizing their physical and emotional presence during their work. They provide consistent care to every patient over time which allows the development of deeper relationships built with understanding, reassurance, support, and empathy. These close bonds reveal the burden carried by the patient that encourages nurses to take a step and to offer more meaningful and compassionate care appropriate to each patient to attend to not only the physical needs but also the emotional and psychological needs. Their regular and extended contact with patients undergoing dialysis enabled the formation of strong therapeutic relationships built

on empathy, emotional support, and trust. This transformation in perception illustrates how immersion in hemodialysis care deepens nurses' professional identity.

Dialysis patients endure rigorous and often painful treatments multiple times a week for years. The nurses in the study shared their daily struggles and, in turn, drew inspiration from their patients' determination and quiet strength. Hemodialysis nurses are not only caregivers but also, they were able to witness the silent battles, the quiet courage, and the strength of their patients. The regular interaction with these patients allows them to appreciate their patient's resilience, determination to heal, and devotion to life-sustaining health treatment. Although it's an exhausting treatment for patients' nurses admire each of their patients to show up in their everyday battles. This admiration becomes so powerful emotional experience for hemodialysis nurse, it inspires and motivates their lives personally and in professional aspects. The emotional connection fostered in these nurse-patient relationships contribute to a deeper appreciation of human endurance, as described by participants who felt personally motivated by the positive attitudes and perseverance of their patients.

It was shown that a striking insight gained from the lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses is their increased awareness of their health. Daily exposure to the long-term consequences of chronic kidney disease served as a constant reminder of the value of early health promotion and prevention. Nurses shared that their perceptions of personal wellness shifted as they observed how lifestyle choices impacted their patients' lives. The data gathered revealed participants found a sense of urgency in valuing their health as they affiliated in a hemodialysis setting. They've realized to give importance and focus on their one's health. This awareness fostered a desire to adopt healthier behaviors and to encourage preventive health in both personal and professional contexts. As noted by participants, the realization of the consequences of neglecting one's health was often a turning point that led them to prioritize self-care. It demonstrates how nurses' exposure to the realities of having chronic illness changes how they view themselves, motivating them to safeguard their health through healthier choices, knowledge, and prevention.

VI. Coping Mechanisms or Support Systems

Despite the challenges, nurses adopt adaptive coping mechanisms that help sustain their well-being and effectiveness in patient care. The following three themes emerged from the participants' narratives: (1) Peer Connection and Workplace Camaraderie, (2) Emotional Reliance on Family and Close Friends, and (3) Personal Coping Rituals and Self-Care Practices.

One of the most prominent sources of emotional strength identified by hemodialysis nurses was the camaraderie shared with their colleagues. Given the routine exposure and by witnessing the chronic illness, patient suffering, and life-threatening scenarios, hemodialysis nurses have a physically and emotionally difficult job. To maintain their well-being and continue providing outstanding care, these nurses use a variety of coping mechanisms and support networks. This aligns with the study of Alodhialah et al. (2024), promoting collaboration and camaraderie among nurses can

alleviate feelings of isolation and enhance their sense of support. The work environment often served as a source of comfort, with participants highlighting the emotional support they received from their co-workers during both routine duties and crises. Hemodialysis nurses echoed that the friendship they build in their co – works or within the dialysis unit serves as an emotional anchor to each of them. They reported that this friendship simply comforts them by merely being able to talk openly with their co – workers. The relationships they have foster send of belonging and understating to each other. For Olson et al. (2020), a supportive work environment can foster a sense of camaraderie, open communication, and shared understanding of the emotional challenges inherent in palliative and end-of-life care nursing. This collegial connection helped reduce feelings of isolation and made it easier for nurses to cope with stress. Simple interactions such as sharing meals, casual conversations during breaks, or emotional debriefings after difficult cases were seen as opportunities to decompress and recharge.

Several hemodialysis nurses in the study emphasized the crucial role of emotional support from family members and close friends. After long and emotionally draining shifts, spending time with loved ones helped nurses restore a sense of balance. Whether through casual bonding or heartfelt conversations, these interactions created a safe and nurturing space for emotional recovery. Spending time with their family members whether it's through casual chats, meals together, or bonding exercises, spending time with family members relieves stress and brings about a sense of calm and offers a safe space for release and recovery after emotionally taxing shifts. Participants described their families as emotional anchors, sources of motivation, understanding, and grounding, who reminded them of life beyond the clinical setting. Close friendships also served as important coping resources, offering empathy and reassurance during difficult times. Nurses rely to reliable friends who provide listening ears, empathy, and support when they are experiencing emotional overload, such as after losing a patient or having a particularly tough workday. Having these relationships outside of work provide them safe space to recharge. In the end, family and close friends act as both emotional safety nets and acts as a fundamental support system that strengthen hemodialysis nurse's resilience and the ability to keep going in a demanding medical setting.

Furthermore, hemodialysis nurses had to face varied sources of stress, whether at work or personal but tried to avoid them such as trying not to create stressful situations or focusing on stress. Participants shared various self-care habits that helped them decompress and sustain emotional resilience. participants reported various personal coping strategies. These included physical activities such as regular exercise, as well as mindfulness practices like meditation and prayer. Engaging in hobbies, spending time alone, and maintaining work-life balance were also mentioned as essential self-care strategies. Practices, such as mindfulness meditation, yoga, and relaxation exercises, can assist nurses in effectively coping with stress and developing emotional resilience. These approaches enhance a feeling of tranquility and emotional equilibrium, allowing nurses to more effectively manage the challenges of their profession. Penque (2020). Participants in the study often noted that taking time for themselves, even briefly, allowed them to recharge and continue providing compassionate care.

VII. Rewarding Aspects of Working with Hemodialysis Patients

It was also discovered that the experience of nurses showed the positive aspects of hemodialysis nursing, particularly the emotional rewards and professional fulfillment nurses derive from their daily work. Based on the lived experiences of participants, two main themes emerged: (1) Daily Expressions of Gratitude Uplift Nurses, and (2) Strong Nurse-Patient Bonds Develop Over Time. These findings illustrate that while the job is physically and emotionally demanding, it also offers moments of deep satisfaction, personal meaning, and sustained motivation.

Hemodialysis nurses repeatedly shared that one of the most meaningful parts of their work is receiving gratitude from patients. Even little acts of gratitude from patients can make a big difference in the emotionally and physically taxing area of hemodialysis care. These expressions, whether a simple “thank you,” a genuine smile, or a kind gesture, were identified as daily moments that ease emotional exhaustion and validate their care efforts. Despite the nature of their tasks, these small tokens of appreciation stood out as powerful motivators and reminders of their value. This is in line with the research conducted by Alodhialah et al. (2024), acknowledging that their efforts, whether through formal awards or simple expressions of gratitude, played a significant role in maintaining their morale and emotional well-being. The consistent gratitude shown by patients not only encourages nurses to continue providing compassionate care but also enhances their emotional well-being and sense of identity as caregivers. The sincere gratitude that nurses receive from patients is essentially more than a simple act of kindness becomes a potent emotional fuel that not only makes them feel better every day but also profoundly sustains their passion, fortifies their resilience, and reaffirms their long-term dedication to the nursing profession. These modest but sincere tokens of appreciation act as a continual reminder of the significance, influence, and passion of their work.

Another significant source of career fulfillment stems from the deep, long-term relationships hemodialysis nurses build with their patients. The most unique and rewarding aspects as a hemodialysis nurse is the chance to form a lasting and meaningful relationship with patients. Hemodialysis nurses often see the same patients for months or even years at a time. Strong ties of empathy, trust, and respect for one another can develop and grow naturally because of this daily connection. The nurses and patients naturally form bonds that go beyond clinical routines. Participants described how regular interaction led to genuine trust, mutual respect, and even friendships. Over time, nurses become consistent sources of comfort, emotional grounding and strength for their patients. They become reliable companions during a long-term challenging journey by frequent interactions and shared experiences, providing not only clinical treatment but also true human connection, presence, and hope. Moreover, over time they shared sense of happiness and connection to celebrate life events together, whether it's a better test results, or even a birthday. Such situations serve as a reminder to the patient and the nurse that they are journeying through life's most significant chapters together, not merely undergoing treatment.

VIII. Type of Support or Resources do Nurses Need in their Workplace

Further insights point to the needs and recommendations of hemodialysis nurses to improve their work environment and ability to provide safe, quality care. Through their lived experiences, several key themes emerged: (1) Adequate Staffing and Manpower, (2) Emotional and Mental Health Support, (3) Equipment, Supplies, and Infrastructure, and (4) Continuous Training and Professional Growth. These findings reflect the need for both structural and emotional support systems within the dialysis setting to promote staff well-being, patient safety, and effective care delivery.

Participants expressed the urgent need for more staff members in dialysis units, particularly fellow nurses, technicians, and on-site physicians. Insufficient manpower was reported to contribute to increased workloads, unfinished responsibilities, and higher chances of burnout. In particular, nurses noted that overlapping responsibilities without clear job descriptions add further pressure, as they often perform duties outside their scope. Insufficient nurse staffing necessitates the provision of other renal care responsibilities, resulting in increased workload, reduced time available for hemodialysis care, and unfinished tasks. The absence of clear job descriptions for hemodialysis care places an additional burden on nurses, who are often required to fulfill the responsibilities of other healthcare teams. Doctors hold the authority in making care decisions, which are subsequently followed by other team members. A steady and consistent presence of physicians is essential for effective patient monitoring, prompt medical decisions for emergencies, and improved coordination of care. Participants emphasized that a more balanced staffing pattern would not only protect patient safety but also enhance teamwork and reduce emotional exhaustion among the staff.

It was shown in the study that the presence of peer support, counseling services, and mental health breaks were among the resources they wished were available. Nurses' health and well-being are affected by the demands of their workplace, and in turn, their well-being affects their work and the people they care for. During their work, hemodialysis nurses encounter physical, mental, emotional, and ethical challenges. Nurses' health and well-being are affected by these stresses and demands of their work, and in turn, their well-being affects their work, including increasing the risk of medical errors and compromising patient safety and care. This reinforces existing literature by Alodhialah et al. (2024), that access to mental health support services can provide nurses with a confidential and safe space to process their emotions, seek guidance, and develop coping strategies. Nurses also stressed the importance of having a safe space to openly share emotions, especially after the death of a patient or during emotionally intense shifts. This includes access to counseling services, peer support groups, and professional mental health programs that can assist individuals in stress management and avoiding emotional exhaustion. Aside from formal programs, nurses report a desire for moral support, a safe space to discuss with colleagues, and opportunities for rest, such as mental health days or scheduled vacations. These things are viewed as necessities rather than luxuries, as they assist nurses in recharging, maintaining compassion, and continuing to provide excellent care.

This is supported by the work of Delgado et al. (2022), who emphasized that providing nurses with access to counseling services can offer a safe space for them to process their emotions and seek professional guidance to manage stress and foster emotional well-being. Without these supports, even the most dedicated nurses may become emotionally withdrawn, compromising both their health and the care they provide.

Participants highlighted the need for better machines, complete supplies, and upgraded dialysis unit infrastructure. The efficiency and safety of dialysis treatments are significantly reliant on the availability and functionality of machines, instruments, and medical supplies. Nurses emphasize the necessity of having adequate and dependable equipment to eliminate treatment delays, enhance patient comfort, and minimize technical errors. Technical issues with machines or cramped workspaces slow down care and increase patient risk. Many many nurses advocate for bigger or modernized dialysis facilities, highlighting that tight or overcrowded conditions hinder smooth functioning and compromise infection control procedures. Therefore, each machine should be at the center of sufficient area to allow easy movement of personnel and resuscitation equipment whenever needed. The layout should have facilities for protecting patients' privacy. A larger, better-organized physical space can assist reduce stress, improve movement, and give patients with a more pleasant and dignified treatment environment.

Hemodialysis nurses recognize the importance of ongoing training and professional development to deliver safe, efficient, and effective patient care. Continuing opportunities are necessary because of the changing nature of dialysis technology, techniques for treatment, and patient needs. The evolving nature of dialysis technology, treatment protocols, and patient needs demands regular opportunities for skill enhancement, knowledge updates, and clinical competency reinforcement. Participants emphasized the need for more regular in-service training, seminars, and learning opportunities. This corroborates the study by Olson et al. (2020) said that the importance of professional growth and continuous learning opportunities resonates with the literature on the role of professional development in promoting resilience. By actively seeking opportunities for growth and acquiring new knowledge and skills, nurses can enhance their sense of competence and confidence, which can contribute to their emotional resilience and their ability to effectively manage the demands of their profession. Olson et al. (2020) Hemodialysis is a rapidly evolving specialty, and participants acknowledged that staying updated with new protocols and technology enhances both competence and confidence. This may include implementing resilience training programs, providing access to counseling services, fostering a supportive organizational culture, and establishing mentorship opportunities for nurses at various career stages. Cabrera-Aguilar et al. (2023). Moreover, equipping nurses with the necessary skills and knowledge early in their careers can better prepare them for the emotional challenges they may encounter in palliative and end-of-life care settings. Alodhialah et al. (2024). Also, supporting this growth not only strengthens care quality but also increases job satisfaction and staff retention. Ultimately, investing in the professional growth of hemodialysis nurses does more than improve care, it empowers nurses, renews their motivation, and contributes to higher retention, confidence, and job satisfaction in the long run.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The study explored the lived experiences of nurses in hemodialysis care within selected centers in Roxas, Isabela. Through in-depth interviews and thematic analysis, the research illuminated the complex interplay of clinical responsibility, emotional labor, and personal resilience that characterizes hemodialysis nursing. The findings highlight that the role of hemodialysis nurses has challenging demands that require technical expertise, emotional strength, and compassionate care.

Despite physical and mental hurdles, many of the nurses derive a strong sense of fulfillment from their meaningful relationships with patients, a shared sense of purpose, and opportunities for professional growth. The study further highlights that despite the intensity of their work, nurses derive fulfillment from small yet meaningful moments such as simple acts of gratitude, as well as deep ties with patients that give them significant emotional rewards. Daily thank-you and long-term nurse-patient connections provide meaningful, joyful, and fulfilling experiences. These interactions contribute to a sense of purpose and motivation, reinforcing nurses' commitment to the profession and validating their efforts and hardships all worthwhile.

The findings identified the lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses, revealing a deeply multifaceted reality. The role of hemodialysis nurses has challenging demands that require technical expertise, emotional strength, and compassionate care. Based on the indicated findings, the study underscores how hemodialysis nurses may sometimes feel exhausted considering the nature of their work of the study. The experience of hemodialysis involves complex, demanding, and specialized nursing care that includes dealing with highly technical machines and skills, establishing a therapeutic and interpersonal relationship because of the frequent visits for treatment, maintenance of physical and mental health, attention to functional limitations and psychological conditions of patients, integrating a palliative approach to patient care, and responding to each need through constant encouragement and education. It clearly states that each hemodialysis nurse's roles and responsibilities are carried out every day and somehow contribute to the feeling of exhaustion. Participants described experiences of encountering patients who are offensive and difficult to handle are one of the biggest challenges they face.

Still, the findings also identify significant challenges that deeply influenced their professional practice, psychological well-being, and perception of care delivery. They know the possibility of complications arising during dialysis treatments, so they remain composed to ensure the quality of treatment. Despite the patient's negative attitudes, they are inspired by them and convey excitement during their treatments. Beyond the clinical aspects, systemic issues were also emphasized. Participants reported difficulties related to staffing shortages, inadequate resources, and operational inefficiencies, all of which impact their ability to deliver quality care. These multifaceted burdens highlight the need for systemic interventions that ensure adequate staffing, emotional support, technical training, and more efficient organizational practices in hemodialysis settings.

The study also revealed a shift in nurses' perceptions through prolonged exposure to patients undergoing dialysis. Participants developed a deeper appreciation for holistic, compassionate care that goes beyond clinical duties. Witnessing the daily strength and perseverance of patients reshaped nurses' views on resilience, not only in their patients but also within themselves. This admiration translated into increased emotional maturity, motivation, and dedication to caregiving.

Throughout the progress of this research, the participants showed various ways of enabling them to cope with personal and professional stress. Hemodialysis nurses rely on strong peer support, family connections, and personal self-care practices to cope with the physical and emotional demands of their work. These provide daily relief, and emotional reliance on family and friends provides a greater sense of security. Individual coping rituals like rest, exercise, and spirituality help nurses retain their resilience and provide compassionate care. These support systems are critical for maintaining their well-being and professional effectiveness.

On the other hand, patient gratitude and long-standing relationships play a critical role in sustaining the motivation and well-being of hemodialysis nurses. These experiences go beyond compensation or recognition and serve as meaningful affirmations of their impact and importance in the lives of others. Participants emphasized that nurturing these connections, their profession becomes not only a job but a calling, rich in purpose, compassion, and human connection.

In summary, the lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses reflect a combination of professional dedication, emotional resilience, and systemic challenge. From proper staffing and manpower to emotional and mental health support, dependable equipment and infrastructure, and opportunities for ongoing training, all play an important role in improving care quality and nursing well-being. Addressing these demands allows healthcare facilities to not only enhance patient outcomes but also maintain a more motivated, capable, and resilient nursing workforce.

Recommendations

In accordance with the findings and conclusions of this study, the researcher's recommendations are proposed to address the challenges and enhance the professional experience of nurses in hemodialysis care:

1. Institutionalize feedback mechanisms through regular meetings or open forums for nurses where nurses can share their concerns, suggestions, and experiences.
2. Encourage nurses to engage in compassionate, whole-person care by providing training on empathy, communication, and therapeutic relationship-building that foster patient-centered and holistic care
3. Recognize the emotional labor of hemodialysis nurses by integrating emotional wellness programs into workplace culture, including regular check-ins, mental health days, or relaxation spaces for recovery.
4. Health care administrators must implement adequate nurse-to-patient

ratios in hemodialysis units to reduce physical exhaustion, prevent burnout, and promote safe, quality care delivery. Improve physician availability by ensuring the regular presence of physicians or nephrologists during dialysis hours. Upgrade equipment and infrastructure to ease workload, enhance competency, promote collaborative care, and prevent treatment interruptions.

5. Implement regular training and continuous professional development programs can help nurses strengthen their positive perceptions of holistic patient care and maintain compassion despite long-term exposure to chronic illness.

6. Organizational policies should consider the importance of work-life balance by implementing flexible scheduling strategies. Rotating shifts, predictable off-days, or self-scheduling systems may grant nurses greater control over their time, reducing burnout and promoting long-term retention in dialysis units.

7. Promote initiatives that celebrate positive patient interactions and gratitude, reinforcing nurses' motivation, fulfillment, and professional commitment.

8. Implement adequate staffing ratios, continuous professional development, emotional wellness initiatives, physician availability, flexible scheduling, feedback mechanisms, and infrastructure upgrades, healthcare institutions can comprehensively respond to the lived experiences of hemodialysis nurses.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher strictly adhered to the ethical guidelines in the preliminary process of conducting this study. Compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) was ensured, safeguarding the confidentiality and privacy of all participants. Furthermore, the study was conducted in accordance with the National Ethical Guidelines for Research Involving Human Participants (2022), which outline the ethical standards for studies involving human participants in the Philippines.

Given the sensitive and reflective nature of the topic, several core ethical principles were carefully observed throughout the research process: beneficence, voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality and anonymity, and non-maleficence.

The principle of beneficence will be practiced by fully disclosing the procedures to the participants to steer clear from any exploitation. The researcher will observe the participants' right to freedom and discomfort. Moreover, the principle of beneficence was upheld by ensuring full disclosure of the study's purpose and procedures to all participants. This transparency aimed to prevent any form of exploitation and promote participants' well-being. Sensitivity was maintained throughout the data collection process, recognizing that sharing professional experiences could evoke emotional responses. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw at any time and to skip questions that caused discomfort. The study also aimed to contribute positively to nursing practice by highlighting the needs and challenges faced by hemodialysis nurses.

Voluntary participation is where people have the free will to exercise to participate in an activity. The participants in this study will be allowed to either participate or withdraw

at any time without any detrimental effect on their participation in the current research and without any unfavorable consequences.

Informed consent is quality information provided to ensure the person who participated in the evaluation was fully informed about the study. The primary purpose of informed consent will be to guarantee the participant can comprehend and be adequately informed about the study to make necessary information about whether to participate in the evaluation.

To protect participants' privacy, all data were treated with strict confidentiality. Personal identifiers were removed from transcripts, and pseudonyms or participant codes were used in all documentation and reporting. Audio recordings, transcripts, and consent forms were securely stored in password-protected files accessible only to the researcher. Findings were presented in a way that ensured individuals could not be identified.

To maintain participants' confidentiality, the researcher will ensure data by assigning code names to keep their identities confidential. Furthermore, their records will be secured by using protected files and keeping survey forms in a locked file. After analyzing and interpreting the data, information will be removed so no one can view the results and information gathered.

The study was designed to ensure that no harm would come to participants as a result of their involvement. Sensitive topics were approached with care, and participants were given the option to skip questions or stop the interview at any point. Debriefing was provided after each interview to ensure participants felt supported.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends profound appreciation and sincere gratitude to all individuals who contributed to the successful completion of the research study. Their support and participation are deeply valued and gratefully acknowledged.

Special thanks are extended to Rev. Fr. Franklin G. Picio, MS, Ph.D., President of the University of La Salette, for his genuine encouragement and inspiring leadership, which served as a source of motivation throughout the research process.

The researcher also expresses deep gratitude to Dr. Madeilyn B. Estacio, Vice President for Academic Affairs, for her unwavering support and uplifting words that inspired the pursuit of academic and professional excellence.

Sincere appreciation is also given to Mr. Benjamin C. Abregado for his insightful advice, valuable comments, and constructive suggestions that significantly enhanced the quality of this study. His patience, guidance, and dedication in clarifying key points of the research were instrumental to its completion.

The researcher acknowledges with heartfelt thanks the encouragement, moral support, and financial assistance provided by their parents, siblings, and special someone. Their unwavering belief, love, and support served as the researcher's constant source of inspiration and strength throughout this journey.

Gratitude is also extended to the research participants for their cooperation, time, and willingness to participate voluntarily in this study. Lastly, above all, the researcher offers humble thanks to Almighty God for granting the wisdom, strength, and perseverance to overcome all challenges and for making the successful completion of this study possible.

REFERENCES

- Ahn, D., Williams, S., Stankus, N., & Saunders, M. (2021). Advance care planning among African American patients on haemodialysis and their end-of-life care preferences. *Journal of Renal Care*, 47(4), 265–278. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jorc.12368>
- Alodhialah, A. M., Almutairi, A. A., & Almutairi, M. (2024). Exploring nurses' emotional resilience and coping strategies in palliative and End-of-Life care settings in Saudi Arabia: a qualitative study. *Healthcare*, 12(16), 1647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12161647>
- Babapour, A., Gahassab-Mozaffari, N., & Fathnezhad-Kazemi, A. (2022). Nurses' job stress and its impact on quality of life and caring behaviors: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-022-00852-y>
- Cabrera-Aguilar, E., Zevallos-Francia, M., Morales-García, M., Ramírez-Coronel, A. A., Morales-García, S. B., Sairitupa-Sanchez, L. Z., & Morales-García, W. C. (2023). Resilience and stress as predictors of work engagement: the mediating role of self-efficacy in nurses. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2023.1202048>
- Camedda, C., Bici, G., Magi, C. E., Guzzon, A., & Longobucco, Y. (2023). The Therapeutic Nurse-Patient Relationship in Hemodialysis: A Pilot Mixed-Method Study on the Perceived Quality of Nurses' Attitudes and Caring Behaviors. *Nursing reports (Pavia, Italy)*, 13(3), 990–1003. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nursrep13030087>
- Cooper, A. L., Brown, J. A., Rees, C. S., & Leslie, G. D. (2020). Nurse resilience: A concept analysis. *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing*, 29(4), 553–575. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inm.12721>
- Delgado, C., Evans, A., Roche, M., & Foster, K. (2022). Mental health nurses' resilience in the context of emotional labour: An interpretive qualitative study. *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing*, 31(5), 1260–1275. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inm.13037>
- Hayes, B., Bonner, A., & Douglas, C. (2021). Haemodialysis work environment contributors to job satisfaction and stress: a sequential mixed methods study. *BMC Nursing*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-015-0110-x>
- Hermann, M. (2023, March 8). The positive effects of expressed gratitude. *Faculty Focus | Higher Ed Teaching & Learning*. <https://www.facultyfocus.com/articles/effective-teaching-strategies/the-positive-effects-of-expressed-gratitude/>
- Huang, J., Barzallo, D. P., Rubinelli, S., Münzel, N., Brach, M., & Gemperli, A. (2020b).

- Professional home care and the objective care burden for family caregivers of persons with spinal cord injury: Cross sectional survey. *International Journal of Nursing Studies Advances*, 3, 100014.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnsa.2020.100014>
- Kallio, H., Kangasniemi, M., & Hult, M. (2022). Registered nurses' perceptions of having a calling to nursing: A mixed-method study. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 78(5), 1473–1482. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15157>
- Kersten, M., Vincent-Höper, S., & Nienhaus, A. (2020). Stress of Dialysis Nurses—Analyzing the buffering role of influence at work and feedback. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(3), 802.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17030802>
- Kersten, M., Vincent-Höper, S., & Nienhaus, A. (2020b). Stress of Dialysis Nurses—Analyzing the buffering role of influence at work and feedback. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(3), 802.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17030802>
- Kim, Y., & Lee, K. (2022). Influence of the workload and years of experience of nurses on hemodialysis quality using Korean National Hemodialysis Adequacy Evaluation data. *INQUIRY the Journal of Health Care Organization Provision and Financing*, 59, 004695802210878. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00469580221087887>
- Lee Ye-Na, Kim Euon Young. (2022). Experiences of Nurses Caring for Hemodialysis Patients: A Qualitative Meta-Synthesis Study. *Korean J Adult Nurse*. 2022 Apr;34(2):168-177. <https://doi.org/10.7475/kjan.2022.34.2.168>
- Mohammed, S., Peter, E., Killackey, T., & Maciver, J. (2021). The “nurse as hero” discourse in the COVID-19 pandemic: A poststructural discourse analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 117, 103887.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2021.103887>
- Molina-Mula, J., & Gallo-Estrada, J. (2020). Impact of Nurse-Patient relationship on quality of care and patient autonomy in Decision-Making. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(3), 835.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17030835>
- National Ethical Guidelines for Research Involving Human Participants. (May 2022)
<https://www.pchrd.dost.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2023/05/2022>
- Naeem, M., Ozuem, W., Howell, K., & Ranfagni, S. (2023). A Step-by-Step Process of thematic analysis to develop a conceptual model in qualitative research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 22.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069231205789>
- Nazly, E. K. A., & Khatib, H. A. (2021). The Knowledge and Educational needs of Nurses regarding pain management of patients on Maintenance Hemodialysis: A Qualitative study. *The Open Nursing Journal*, 15(1), 93–102.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1874434602115010093>
- Olson, R. E., Smith, A., Good, P., Neate, E., Hughes, C., & Hardy, J. (2020). Emotionally reflexive labour in end-of-life communication. *Social Science & Medicine*, 291, 112928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.112928>
- Penque, S. (2020). Mindfulness to promote nurses' well-being. *Nursing Management*, 50(5), 38–44. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.numa.0000557621.42684.c4>
- Staaf, K., Fernström, A., & Uhlin, F. (2022). Preconditions that facilitate cannulation in

arteriovenous fistula: A mixed-methods study. *Journal of Renal Care*, 49(4), 264–277. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jorc.12448>

Yamamoto, K., Nasu, K., Nakayoshi, Y., & Takase, M. (2024). Sustaining the nursing workforce - exploring enabling and motivating factors for the retention of returning nurses: a qualitative descriptive design. *BMC Nursing*, 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-024-01900-5>